

Role of Surya Namaskar in The Overall Health of Adolescents

Paper Id : 20333 Submission Date : 2025-07-04 Acceptance Date : 2025-07-20 Publication Date : 2025-07-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16162805

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Awadhesh Kumar Shukla

Research Scholar
Department Of Physical Education
DDU Gorakhpur University
Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Vijay Chahal

Professor
Department Of Physical Education
DDU Gorakhpur University
Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

In today's materialistic and mechanical age, in which the human ability is constantly declining, activity is a biological quality of human beings and if they lose it, they cannot survive for long. People aged 10-19 years are known as adolescents. This is the period of growth and development. In this age of mechanization, in a hectic life and competitive environment and in a life full of pressure and tension, it is no less than a challenge for adolescents to maintain their health. Surya namaskar, or Sun Salutation, is a dynamic series of yogic posture practiced widely in traditional Indian yoga. Daily practice of Surya Namaskar is no less than a Sanjivani in maintaining their health, providing them physical and mental fitness, increasing their immune system, relieving them from pressure and tension, balancing the vital energy and developing their overall health.

Keywords

Surya Namaskar, Overall Health, Yoga, Adolescents.

Introduction

The present time is the age of machines. It is not possible to imagine human life without it. It has covered human life in the same way as a thick cloud covers the sky. Activity is a biological quality of man. It is the basis of human life. Without it, he cannot survive for long. As he became a dependent on these machines, his abilities and capabilities decreased. The practice of Surya namaskar is useful and important in maintaining physical abilities and their growth and development. The World Health Organization has defined adolescents as persons in the age group of 10-19 years and youth as persons in the age group of 15-24 years, while young people are included in the range of 10-24 years. Many changes come in the life of adolescents. Surya namaskar is very useful in solving these. Surya namaskar is no less than a boon in developing the overall health of adolescents. The present time is very hectic. People are less in the role of cooperation and more in the role of competition. In this fast-paced life and competitive environment, achieving your goals and maintaining health is no less than a challenge. Teenagers are also not untouched by these problems. They have to go through many problems, pressures and stress in achieving their goals, desires and aspirations. Surya namaskar is no less than a medicine for solving all these problems, pressures and stress. Surya namaskar is an ancient medical method by our ancient sages and sages, which teenagers can include in their lifestyle and achieve their complete health, develop their health and also manage their pressure and stress effectively.

Objective of study

1. To analyze the theoretical foundation of Surya namaskar in yoga literature.
2. To explore the impact of Surya namaskar on the physical, mental, and emotional health of adolescents

Review of Literature

1. Hatha Yoga Pradipika and Gheranda Samhita describe the importance of asanas and breathing in balancing the doshas (body energies).
2. Bhavanani et al. (2011) found improved cardiovascular endurance and muscular strength in school children practicing Surya Namaskar daily.
3. Deshpande et al. (2016) noted significant improvement in BMI, self-esteem, and academic performance among adolescents involved in yoga-based programs.

Main Text

Surya Namaskar:

Surya Namaskar means gratitude towards the Sun or worship of the Sun. Sun is the center of energy universally. All living beings and plants are directly or indirectly dependent on the Sun. Surya Namaskar is prevalent since ancient times. The glory of the Sun has been described in the Rigveda. In the Rigveda, the Sun has been called the soul of the world. Yajurveda has considered the Sun as the eye of God by saying "Chakso Suryao Jayat". There are 12 mudras in Surya Namaskar. There are 12 mantras. There are 12 phases of the Sun. There

are also 12 zodiac signs in a year. Therefore, the 12 mudras or asanas of Surya Namaskar have been scientifically arranged by our sages. There are seven chakras in our body which are energy bodies. Surya Namaskar works to awaken and balance them in an organized manner.

Steps of Surya Namaskar:

1- Namaskar asana 2- Hastottanasana 3- Pada Hastasana 4 - Ashwasanchalanasana 5- Parvatasana 6- Sash tang Namaskar asana 7- Bhujangasana 8- Parvatasana 9- Ashwasanchalanasana 10- Pada Hastasana 11- Hastottanasana 12—Namaskar asana

Scientific secret of Surya Namaskar:

Indian sages have said that different parts of the body are governed by different deities. Among the seven chakras of our body, the Manipur Chakra which is located behind the navel is known as Surya Chakra or Solar Plexus. It is also called the second brain. It is connected to the Sun. The act of Surya Namaskar plays an important role in balancing and awakening this chakra. Then, when this chakra is awakened, the human body gets energy, purity and power. Man gets free from negative energies. Ayurveda has been considering the Sun as the God of health since its inception. In Physical Culture Monthly Magazine July 1926, Dr. Gardner wrote that sit naked in the sun. Sun is the king of doctors and medicines. Scriptures say that the sun is the provider of health. According to Ayurveda, Surya Namaskar helps in balancing the three doshas, Vata, Pitta and Kapha. Ancient Indian sages have said that different energies control different parts of the body. The solar plexus located behind the navel is connected to the sun. Regular practice of Surya Namaskar increases the size of the solar plexus which increases our creativity, decision making ability and self-confidence.

Why do Surya Namaskar every day:

In today's materialistic mechanical age where there is an atmosphere of competition everywhere, due to which the teenagers are becoming stressed. Teens are becoming unhealthy due to unbalanced daily routine, night routine, seasonal routine, polluted environment, adulterated food, junk food, consumption of food items made of spices. To solve all these problems, it is necessary to include Surya Namaskar, which is a complete exercise, in your daily routine.

Although Surya Namaskar can be done anytime, but the best time is to do it at sunrise on an empty stomach. With its regular practice, the muscles remain in tone. Blood flow remains balanced. Abdominal muscles become strong. Muscles of hands and legs become strong. Abdominal fat is reduced. Wrists become strong. Coordination is established in the body.

Surya namaskar and Sapta Chakras:

There are seven energy bodies or centers of power in the subtle body of a human being. These are known as chakras in the language of yoga. These are Mooladhara, Swadhisthana, Manipura, Anahat, Vishuddhi, Agya, and Sahasrara. Practicing Surya namaskar puts pressure on these chakras, they get stimulated and they get awakened. As a result, qualities like inner awareness, intuition, concentration and perception etc. develop. Pranam Asana awakens Anahat Chakra, Hasta Utthan Asana awakens Vishuddhi Chakra, Pada Hastasana awakens Swadhisthana Chakra, Ashwa Sanchala asana awakens Agya Chakra, Parvatasana awakens Vishuddhi Chakra, Ashtanga Namaskar awakens Manipura Chakra, Bhujangasana awakens Swadhisthana Chakra and balances their energy. Introspection, creativity, concentration, and balance of energy are essential for a balanced life of teenagers.

Surya namaskar and Respiratory System:

Surya namaskar is a process of rhythmic breathing. In Hastottanasana, the lungs are completely filled with oxygenated prana vayu and in Pada Hastasana, deep breath is exhaled which empties the lungs. Due to this effect, all the alveoli become active. The amount of oxygen in the blood increases. The efficiency of

the respiratory system increases through the process of rhythmic inhalation and exhalation. A strong respiratory system is essential for the good health of adolescents.

Surya Namaskar and Circulatory System:

Practice of Surya Namaskar improves the functioning of the heart without harming the heart muscles. The resulting increase in blood flow speeds up the removal of waste material and provides fresh oxygen and nutrients to all cells. The heart muscles are strengthened and the blood vessels of the heart, the coronary arteries are stimulated to grow or dilate, thereby improving circulation and reducing the chances of heart attack. Padahasthasana and Parvatasana aid the return of blood from the lower part of the body to the heart, stretching the leg muscles and in the inverted position the force of gravity acts on the return of blood. Other asanas squeeze blood out of the organs and aid in the exchange of waste products for oxygen and nutrients at the cell blood vessel wall junction. The process of growth and development accelerates in the adolescent period. For which it is necessary for the circulatory system to function in a balanced state to deliver oxygen and nutrients to various parts of the body.

Surya Namaskar and Digestive System:

During Surya Namaskar, the entire digestive system is stretched and pressed alternately, massaging all the abdominal organs. Pada Hastasana and Bhujangasana are particularly powerful in pressing and stimulating the abdominal organs. This not only removes waste material from digestion, but also increases the digestive fire, increases appetite and promotes complete and rapid absorption of food. Proper digestion is a major factor in overall health. Proper digestion is necessary for everyone. Adolescence is known as the period of growth and development. Its usefulness increases even more during this period.

Surya Namaskar for Teenagers:

In today's time, in this hustle and bustle, a person has to face many problems. Teenagers are also not untouched by this. They also have to face many problems at this time. Today, the youth have to work in a competitive environment, due to which it is natural for them to have pressure and stress. Surya Namaskar reduces their pressure and stress. It calms the mind and helps in increasing concentration and helps them in achieving overall health. Therefore, they should include Surya Namaskar in their daily life.

Surya Namaskar for Women Teens:

Women have to face many problems during adolescence. Surya Namaskar is no less than a boon in controlling the weight of women. It puts pressure on the abdominal muscles, due to which fat does not accumulate around the stomach. Surya Namaskar plays an important role in regulating the menstrual cycle of women and making delivery easier. Thus, women should include Surya Namaskar in their daily life and practice it regularly.

Conclusion

Yoga and Ayurveda were ancient Indian systems of medicine by adopting which people remained healthy and long-lived. In the present times of competition, its usefulness has increased even more. Surya Namaskar is equally useful for the elderly, children, adolescents, men and women. It develops all dimensions of our health such as physical, mental, social, emotional and spiritual aspects. Surya Namaskar strengthens our spine. It stimulates and balances all the systems of the body. In the present times, by including Surya Namaskar in our daily life or by making it a part of our daily lifestyle, we can all get the benefits of overall health.

References

1. Saraswati, S. S. (1996). *Asana Pranayama Mudra Bandh, Bihar India Bihar School of Yoga, Yog Publication Trust.*
2. Swami, M. (1998). *Hath Yoga Pradipika, Yoga Publication Trust, Munger.*
3. Gharote, M. L. & Ganguly, S. K. (2001). *Teaching methods of yogic practices, kaivalyaadhama, Lonavala.*
4. Saraswati, S. N. (2002). *Yoga and Total Health.*
5. Vivekananda, R. (2005). *Practical Yoga Psychology. Yoga Publication Trust, Munger.*
6. Saxena, O. P. (2010). *Vrihad Prakritik chiktisa, Hindi Sewa Sadan, Mathura.*
7. Saraswati, S. S. (2013). *Surya Namaskar, Yoga Publication Trust, Munger, Bihar, India.*
8. Sharma, M. K. (2014). *Effect of Surya namaskar on stress level. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Volume 2, Issue.1.*
9. Deorari, M. et al. "A Study on the Effect of Surya Namaskar on Emotional Maturity and Psychological Wellbeing", *International Journal of Yoga and Allied Sciences (ISSN: 2278-5159) Volume: 1, Issue: 2.*

10. Ravindra R. et al, "Effect of Surya namaskar on selected physical fitness variable of stay-at-home Peoples of Nashik city", *Entire Research*, March 2021, Page no-439.
11. *The physiology of yoga*, Andrew McGonigle, MD, Matthew Huy. Description: Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics, [2023].